

A Study On Customer Satisfaction Towards Paperless Banking Service In Tirunelveli District

P.Ponmalar¹ Dr. E. Angel Saral Rose²

Reg no: 20121241012003

¹Ph.D Part time Research Scholar Department of Commerce and Research centre
Sarah Tucker College, Perumalpuram

²Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce and Research centre
Sarah Tucker College, Perumalpuram Tirunelveli-7

Mail id: ponmalarstc@gmail.com

Abstract:

In the banking sector, various electronic delivery channels are increasingly used for delivering products and services at the convenience of customer at low cost. Paperless banking is one among them. The banking industry has been rapidly developing the use of Paperless banking as an efficient and viable tool to create customer value. It is one of the popular services offered by the traditional banks to provide speedier and reliable services to online users. With the rapid development of computer technology as a commercial tool Paperless banking can be used to attract more customers to perform banking transactions in related banks. However, the main problem of Paperless banking faced by the provider is that a large number of the banks' customers are not willing to use the Paperless banking services offered. This happened due to the services offered through Paperless banking yet to satisfy their customers. Customer satisfaction is an important factor to help banks to sustain competitive advantages. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to search and examine the factors which influence customer satisfaction towards Paperless banking. The four factors which can influence customer satisfaction toward Paperless banking include service quality, web design, security and privacy and convenience. With the use of a questionnaire survey, 100 working adults participated in this study have provided valuable feedback and responses pertaining to the above factors that influence customers' decision to do Paperless banking. The results of this research showed that web design, convenience and security are closely linked to customer satisfaction toward Paperless banking

Keywords: Paperless banking, service quality, customer satisfaction, security; privacy.

Introduction

Paperless banking is an integrated system that provides their customers a flexible, convenient and inexpensive platform with integrated services including online bank balance enquiry and savings accounts, money market accounts, certificates of deposit, credit cards, home equity loans, home mortgage, insurance, investment services, portfolio management, and other related financial services. Paperless banking has gained higher acceptance from the customers who are highly supportive of new technology. Paperless banking acts as a kind of financial intermediation which makes transaction through Internet. In the banking industry, Paperless banking is the industry which uses computer technology to provide better services to the customers and help the development of banking practices. Technological innovations are one of the effective ways to increase the level of service quality to satisfy customer needs. Through the advanced technology and innovation in the financial and banking sectors, Paperless

banking has become more familiar to the customers of traditional banks. Internet banking is offered by the retail banking in many developed countries and customers can make transactions without having to leave their homes or workplace. In addition, Paperless banking can help customers to manage their finances more efficiently.

Types Of Electronic Banking In India

The following three basic kinds of Paperless banking are being practised in the marketplace:

1. Informational - This is the basic level of electronic banking. Typically, the bank has marketing

information about the bank's products and services on a stand-alone server. Risk involved in such kind of Paperless banking is relatively low as informational systems typically have no path between the server and the bank's internal network. This level of Paperless banking can be provided by the bank or outsourced. While the risk to a bank is relatively low, the server or website may be vulnerable to alteration. Appropriate controls

therefore must be in place to prevent unauthorized alterations to the bank's server or website.

2. Communicative - This type of electronic banking system allows some interaction between the bank's systems and the customer. The interaction may be limited to e-mail, account inquiry, loan applications, or static file updates (name and address changes). Because of these servers may have a path to the bank's internal networks, the risk is higher with this configuration than with informational systems. Appropriate controls need to be in place to prevent, monitor and alert management of any unauthorized attempt to access the bank's internal networks and computer systems. Virus controls also become much more critical in this environment.

3. Transactional - This level of electronic banking allows customers to execute transactions. Since path typically exists between the server and the bank's or outsourcer's internal network, this is the highest risk architecture and must have the strongest controls. Customer transactions can include accessing accounts, paying bills, transferring funds, etc.

Statement Of The Problem

Here the necessity for selecting a problem in research is defined. The problem is stated as to what extent the respondents are satisfied with **PAPERLESS BANKING SERVICES** and **FACILITIES**, the difficulties faced by them in getting the required information and which factors are creating more influence on the respondents.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To study the socio economic characteristics of the sample respondents
2. To measure the satisfaction level of the respondents towards Paperless banking services
3. To study the problems faced by the respondents
4. To offer suggestions and recommendation for further improvement of Paperless banking services.

Review Of Literature:

Shilpan Vyas (2012)¹ in their article "*Impact of E-Banking on Traditional Banking Services*" stated that Internet banking, any inquiry or transaction is processed online without any reference to the branch (anywhere banking) at any time. Providing Internet banking is increasingly becoming a

"need to have" than a "nice to have" service. The net banking, thus, now is more of a norm rather than an exception in many developed countries due to the fact that it is the cheapest way of providing banking services. E-banking provides enormous benefits to consumers in terms of ease and cost of transactions, either through Internet, telephone or other electronic delivery. Electronic finance (E-finance) has become one of the most essential technological changes in the financial industry. E-finance as the provision of financial services and markets using real-time transfer and get the feedback information about payment from our bank when the client does shopping in the appointed web-site. E-banks are easy to set up, so lots of new entrants will arrive. „Old-world“ systems, cultures and structures will not encumber these new entrants. Instead, they will be adaptable and responsive. E-banking gives consumers much more choice. Consumers will be less inclined to remain loyal. The electronic devices which perform interact with customers and communicate with other banking system is called electronic banking delivery channels.

Mr. Lakshmi Narayana.KMr., Sri Hari.V, Dr.P. Paramashivaiah (2013)² in their article "*A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Online Banking services with reference to Bangalore city.*" stated that customers expect highest quality services from banks which, if fulfilled, could result in significantly improved customer satisfaction levels. Focuses on investigating the major factors that influence online customers' satisfaction with the overall service quality of their banks. Assessing the power of these factors in the context of Online (Internet) banking and would, therefore, help the bank management not only in improving the level of satisfaction but also strengthening the bond between the banks and their customers, thereby helping them to retain and/or expand their overall customer base. Banks and financial corporations have been at the forefront of this Internet and technology adoption process. Online banking refers to the automated delivery of banking products and services directly to customers through electronic communication channels, most notably the Internet. Online banking is also called E-banking or PC banking. Align their offerings to the constantly evolving customer needs and developments in technology, it

also serves to replace some of traditional bank functions, thereby reducing significant overheads associated with bank branches. Online banking, to make a customer's banking experience more convenient, efficient, and effective, it becomes even more important to ascertain the customers' perception of the overall service quality and their satisfaction with the current online banking services.

D.N.V.Krishna Reddy, Dr.M.Sudhir Reddy (2015)³ in their article "*A Study On Customer's Perception And Satisfaction Towards Electronic Banking In Khammam District*" stated that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have brought about a lot of changes in almost all aspects of life. In the Banking Industry, it has been in the form of E-Banking or Online Banking or Internet Banking, which is now replacing the traditional banking mechanism. E-Banking has a lot of benefits which add value to enhance customers' satisfaction in terms of better quality of service offerings and simultaneously enable the banks gain more competitive advantage over other competitors. E-Banking is a combination of two, Electronic technology and Banking." "Electronic Banking is a process by which a customer performs banking Transactions electronically without visiting a brick-and-mortar institutions." "E-Banking denotes the provision of banking and related service through Extensive use of information technology without direct recourse to the bank by the customer." the satisfaction of the customer majorly influenced the convenience, awareness, and responsiveness. In the present technology society, most of the banking customer prefer and switch to e-banking facilities. So the banker may improve their services, loyalty to customers and their retention by increasing awareness of other age groups and concentrating on the factors contributing customer satisfaction. customer is different so bank should concentrate on all the age group of customers for betterment of e-banking banks.

Ms. M.Esther Krupa. (2016)⁴ in their article "A Study on Customer Satisfaction Towards E-Banking Services in Coimbatore City" banking is one of the emerging trends in the Indian banking and is playing a unique role in strengthening the banking sector and improving service quality. It has enabled the

banks to handle the payments electronically faster and in large volumes. Several initiatives have been taken by the Government of India as well as the Reserve bank to facilitate the development of e-banking in India. The Reserve bank is monitoring and receiving the legal and other requirements of e-banking on a continuous basis to ensure that e-banking would develop on sound lines and e-banking related challenges would not pose a threat to financial stability. E-banking reaps benefits for both banks and its customers. From the banks' perspective, e-banking has enabled banks to lower operational costs through the reduction of physical facilities and reduced waiting time in branches resulting in potential increase in sales performance and a larger global reach. From the customer's perspective, e-banking allows customers to perform a wide range of banking transactions electronically via the bank's website anytime and anywhere. The customers expect many services with the various delivery modes which is speed and secure. The banking industry has been considerably influenced by the expansion of technology which has given way to the modern banking system to take over the traditional banking system.

Dr. Pratima Merugu (2018)⁵ in his article "*Customer Satisfaction towards Online Banking With Reference To Greater Visakhapatnam City*" stated that customers and deliver customer satisfaction. A fundamental understanding of factors causing customer satisfaction in online banking has attained greater prominence as more and more banks compete to offer superior services to their clients making it imperative for banks to align their strategies in response to changing customer's needs and technology. apply the modified SERVQUAL model in the context of Internet banking to describe how customers perceive online service quality' The Internet has emerged as a major force in the financial service sector. The corollary of this phenomenon has been the appearance of fierce competition among banks providing online services to their customer/clients. Online/Internet banking is an electronic payment system that enables customers of a financial institution to conduct financial transactions on a website operated by the institution, such as a retail bank, virtual bank, credit union or building society. Online banking is also referred as

Internet banking, e-banking, virtual banking and by some other terms. Online banking is becoming a popular tool to attract customers and deliver customer value and satisfaction. customer satisfaction is a critical factor for online banking service providers to maintain and improve their profitability. Online banking has gained popularity for a number of reasons, including convenience, cheaper, multifunctional services, trendy and hassle free. Online banking services have emerged as a decisive factor for customers when choosing a bank. Banks offer several online products and service to their customers, Customer satisfaction is increasingly recognized as a main pillar for success in the business environment and also a key factor for the survival and growth of the banking sector. Providing superior service quality enhances customer satisfaction and encourages more participation among customers. High Service quality deliverance leads to overall customer satisfaction.

C K Sunith (2019)⁶ in his article "*Customer Satisfaction in E-Banking Services*" stated that Electronic banking incorporates systems that enable individual customers to access their accounts, transact with speed and obtain current and updated information on latest financial products and services through public or private networks. It accommodates a variety of platforms such as internet banking, telephonic and television based banking, automated teller services, mobile phone banking as well as personal computer based and offline banking services. Since most of these technology services have become popular in our country, customers now have every opportunity to will fully choose and exploit the features provided by advanced electronics and information technologies such as automatic teller machines, internet, mobile phones, personal digital assistants and personal computers and experience electronic banking services

through privileges and facilities delivered with assistance from modern technologies. Banks will have to incur capital costs and incorporate advanced technologies to save on operating costs and to earn customer goodwill, but must extract maximum returns from such assets while cutting down operating expenses at the same time. conceptual model that competency and efficiency of banking services, accurate and timely information, efficient web portal management as well as customer relationship management, demonstration and training of customers and economy of services determine the extent of satisfaction of E Banking customers. Customer is distinguished from a consumer in the sense that a customer pays for a product or service while a consumer is the end user who experiences a product or service.

Methodology:-

This section describe the methodology which include collection of data, construction of questionnaire and frame work analysis.

Collection Of Data

The primary data have been collected directly from the mobile banking customer and internet banking customer through on questionnaire. Secondary data have been collected from standard books, articles, magazines, encyclopaedia and internet.

• **Primary data**

The study mainly based upon the primary data. Interview schedule method is used to collect the data from the respondents. Sample size of "100" respondents have been appended in the research report.

• **Secondary data**

The substantiate and to support the primary data required particular have been gathered by referring the reputed journals, magazines, standard news paper and book. Some of the information has been gathered from authorized web source.

Analysis Of Data

Socio Economic Factor of Respondents

Table - 1

Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	60	60
	Female	40	40
	Total	100	100
Age	Below 30 years	15	15
	31 – 40 years	30	30
	41 – 50 years	15	15

	51-60 years	18	18
	Above 61 years	22	22
	Total	100	100
Literacy Level	School Level	10	10
	UG Level	40	40
	PG Level	28	28
	Professional Level	22	22
	Total	100	100
Religion	Hindu	55	55
	Christian	25	25
	Muslim	20	20
	Total	100	100
Current Occupation	Government Sector	14	14
	Private Sector	46	46
	Entrepreneur	20	20
	Professional	20	20
	Total	100	100
Monthly Income	Below Rs.20,000	25	25
	Rs.20,001– Rs.40,000	35	35
	Rs.40,001– Rs.60,000	30	30
	above Rs.60,000	10	10
	Total	100	100
Paperless Banking Transaction Used for Per Month	1000 and below	15	15
	1001- 10000	15	15
	10001- 20000	30	30
	20001-30000	25	25
	Above 30000	15	15
	Total	100	100
Using paperless banking Applications	Less than 6 months	35	35
	6 months - 1 year	30	30
	1 year – 2 years	11	11
	more than 2 years	24	24
	Total	100	100
Purpose of using paperless banking	Balance Enquiry	15	15
	Mini Statement	15	15
	Mobile Top-up	15	15
	Fund transfer	30	30
	24 hrs usage facility	25	25
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It this research study, there are 60% of the respondents Male and 40% of the respondents are Female. It is inferred from the study that 15% of the respondents age below 30years and 30% of the respondents age 31-40 years respectively users in paperless banking services. Mostly 40% of the respondents literacy level at UG level and 28% of the respondents at the PG levels.55% of the respondents are Hindu and 25% of the respondents are Christian 20%

of the respondents are m banking used in Muslim.46% of the respondents are Private sectors and 20% of the respondents are Government staffs. It is inferred from the study that 25% of the respondents get an income range from below Rs.20,000 monthly incomes, and 35% of the respondents get an income range below Rs.21, 000 – Rs.40,000. Most 15% of the respondents in the study Paperless Banking Transaction Used for Per Month

Rs.1, 000-10,000 and 15% of the respondents used below Rs.1, 000. Most of the respondents in the study 24% Using paperless banking Applications services

more than 2 years and 35% of the respondents using 6 months - 1 year. Most of the 30% of the respondents Purpose of using paperless banking

Interest on paperless internet banking

Table - 2

SI. No	Particular	No.of Respondents (W)	Value (X)	WX	Rank
1	Quality of service	27	5	135	I
2	Technology used	18	4	72	II
3	Trust	22	3	66	III
4	Cost effectiveness	13	2	26	IV
5	Ease of used	20	1	20	V
	Total	100		319	

Source: Computed table

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mean score} &= \frac{\sum WX}{\sum W} \\ &= \frac{319}{100} \\ &= 3.19 \end{aligned}$$

The above table shows that out of 100 respondent's quality of service occupy first rank, Technology used secured second rank, Trust obtains third rank, Cost effectiveness occupies fourth rank, and Ease of used obtains fifth rank.

Hence, it is clear that quality of service got first rank.

Findings:

The findings of the present revealed the following.

- 60% of the respondents are male.
- 30% of the respondents age group laid down 31-40.
- 40% of the respondents are UG level.
- 55% of the respondents are Hindu.
- 46% of the respondents are private sector.
- 35% of the respondents were laid on between Rs.20000-40000.
- 30% of the respondents are using paperless banking for transaction.
- 35% of the respondents are using paperless banking applications.
- 30% of the respondents are using paperless banking for fund transfer.
- Interest on paperless internet banking got I Rank.

Suggestions

- Most of the web based problems such as low speed, connection lost while processing transactions etc may not be within the reach of banks and they may not have much to solve these problems. However, for problem of account temporarily locked by bank. The bank can make the customers aware that their account will be temporarily

locked if they make multiple incorrect password entry, to ensure security. What the banks can do in this regard is to advice users to choose passwords which are easy to remember for them but difficult to be guessed by others.

- Quickness of the web page on bank's portal site loading. This has to do with the speed of the

online system, so management would need to increase the speed or bandwidth for effective browsing and opening of pages; especially pages with video and pictures require high bandwidth.

- Prompt responses to customer request. This relates to customer relationship. This requires training of more efficient customer service staff who would be able to handle customer request promptly.

- Paperless banking system's ability to guide customer to resolve problems. Customer may have many problems in accessing and utilising online banking portals, it is the responsibility of the management to ensure that all diverse customer problems are attended to by technicians with expert knowledge to resolve customers' problems.

Conclusion

Paperless banking seems poised to become an important part of the Indian banking sector in the years to come. The banking today is re-defined and re-engineered with the use of Information Technology and it is sure that the future of banking will offer more sophisticated services

to the customers with the continuous product and process innovations. Thus, there is a paradigm shift from the seller's market to buyer's market in the industry and finally it affected at the bankers level to change their approach from "conventional banking to convenience banking" and "mass banking to class banking". The shift has also increased the degree of accessibility of a common man to bank for his variety of needs and requirements. Analysts claim that Paperless banking holds lots of potential with the emergence of growing Internet awareness among customers, integration of banking services with e-commerce service, the increasing reach of the Internet and the entry of global players in the banking sector. Reserve Bank of India has come out with Paperless banking related guidelines.

"Customer Satisfaction towards Online Banking With Reference To Greater Visakhapatnam City"
International Journal of Management, Technology And Engineering
Volume8,IssueXII

7. **C K Sunith (2019)** -"*Customer Satisfaction in E-Banking Services*"
International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI) ISSN (Online): 2319 – 8028, ISSN (Print): 2319 – 801X www.ijbmi.org || Volume 8 Issue 01 Ver. II.

Reference:

1. **Shilpan Vyas (2012)** " *Impact of E-Banking on Traditional Banking Services* " The Icfai journal of Professional Banker,February pp 7-10.
2. **Mr. Lakshmi Narayana.KMr., Sri Hari.V, Dr.P. Paramashivaiah (2013)** -"*A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Online Banking services with reference to Bangalore city.* " International Journal of Research in Management ISSN 2320 – 2939 (Print) ISSN 2320-2793 (online) Let your Research be Global search– An Ultimate search of Truth-Reforms through Research Vol- 2 No. 2.
3. **N.V.Krishna Reddy, Dr.M.Sudhir Reddy (2015)** -"*A Study On Customer's Perception And Satisfaction Towards Electronic Banking In Khammam District*"IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM) e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 17, Issue 12 .Ver. II (Dec. 2015), PP 20-27
4. www.iosrjournals.org.
5. **Ms. M.Esther Krupa. (2016)** -"*A Study on Customer Satisfaction Towards E- Banking Services in Coimbatore City* " Indian Journal Of Applied Research. Volume : 6 | Issue :
6. **Dr. Pratima Merugu (2018)** -